

Interview Guideline

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May 2023

The main objective of our study is to **explore opportunities and challenges when working with requirements that are written with a regulation as the source**, which we aim at addressing by answering the following research questions:

RQ1 What are the engineering practices when working with requirements with regulation as source?

RQ2 What are associated challenges encountered by SE teams when working with requirements with regulation as source?

RQ3 Which of those challenges can be addressed via automated approaches (to which extent)?

In the long run, we aim at understanding what the potential of automation in the field of handling requirements in regulated contexts is and develop a sensible approach along those limitations.

Disclaimer

Provided your agreement, I would like to record this interview for subsequent transcription. The transcription itself and any findings will be used for research purposes and the eventual publication. Any personal information and details that would allow to identify the project will be anonymized, and the final results will be shared for approval. Do you consent to the recording?

Background

1. What is your role and responsibilities in the projects? Please provide a short overview of the tasks that you perform in your role.
2. How many years of experience in this field and in the company do you have?
3. What are exemplary projects that you are working on and in which you need to handle requirements in regulated contexts?
4. Please select and briefly describe one exemplary project that you deem representative for a highly regulated setting.

5. What are the main responsibilities of itestra in that project?
6. With which regulations is the project and SW product required to be compliant?

RQ1

1. What are the main artefacts (documents, diagrams, etc.) that you use and create in the engineering process when working with requirements with regulation as source?
 - What are the artefacts that you receive from the customer and what do you need to deliver?
 - Who is responsible for each artefact?
2. With whom do you directly interact when it comes to handling requirements that relate to regulations?
 - Are there any external stakeholders in the process? (customer side, external legal experts, or regulatory bodies)?
 - How do different stakeholders interact/communicate within the engineering process?
3. How do you process and implement regulations in your projects? What related activities/tasks are you involved in?
 - Do you have a structured procedure or templates for requirements (e.g. guidelines)?
4. How do you ensure the system fulfils especially those requirements that relate to regulations?
5. Who is responsible (and liable) for compliance with the regulations?
6. What tools do you use in the engineering process when working with requirements with regulation as a source?
 - What was your experience in the use of these tools?
 - (if any tools for automation are used) How are these technologies introduced? (if not) has the possibility been discussed?

RQ2

1. In your opinion, what are the biggest challenges that arise when handling requirements that are sourced from regulations?
2. What has been the most challenging experience for you? (prioritizing)
3. How could the current engineering process be improved from your perspective? What would be helpful for your work?

RQ3

1. What are your thoughts on the potential of automation to address some of the challenges faced by SE teams when working with requirements in regulated contexts?
2. In your opinion, in which parts of the engineering process could automation be applied in a beneficial way?
3. In your opinion, which would be the conditions and prerequisites under which you would consider automation feasible and useful in the project? For example are there any quality attributes you consider important (e.g. precision/recall)?

Closing

1. Will it be possible to have access to the relevant documentation and artefacts from the mentioned projects?
2. Is there some other aspect to discuss that I may have missed?
3. Can you refer anyone else who could provide further insight into this research?